

Sexual violence mitigation in realizing a violence-free campus

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ABSTRACT

Sexual violence occurs in higher education institutions. Sexual violence mitigation studies have a theoretical novelty using Giddens' structuring of the problem of sexual violence. The research aims to determine the relationship between policy stakeholders, lecturers, students, and education staff; know the obstacles and challenges; and know the model of sexual violence mitigation in higher education. The research used qualitative with case studies of three higher education in Indonesia. The informant consisted of 27 respondents: students, lecturers, and education staff. Data collection through interviews, documentation, observation, and focus group discussion (FGD). Data processing using the NVivo 12 Plus application; Publish or Perish; and VOSviewer. Data analysis using: data reduction; present data; and conclusion. This research shows that the relationship is very important between policymakers and lecturers, students, and education staff in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence. Cooperation of all parties in facing challenges in handling and prevention of sexual violence on campuses that have obstacles, to realize a campus free from violence. This study concludes that realizing a campus that is free from sexual violence can be implemented on campuses in Indonesia. Recommendations for participatory and gender-responsive sexual violence mitigation policy models are applied in higher education in Indonesia.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sexual violence can occur everywhere in family settings, public spaces, and even in higher education institutions. Sexual violence is an important issue discussed around the world: sexual violence in 10 countries in Europe [1], 24 countries in Europe and Africa [2]; 25 countries in Africa and the Americas [3], Australia [4], Chile [5], America [6], Brazil [7], Spain [8], Nigeria [9], Ethiopia [10] cases of sexual violence in higher education in the world are increasing. There was a 26.4% increase in victims of violence at the undergraduate level, and 6.9% of undergraduate education was male [11].

Sexual violence occurrence in higher education is discussed also in the Asian Region including in Indonesia. Various studies of sexual violence in higher education occurred in Japan, South Korea, Singapore, and Taiwan [3], [12]; Vietnamese [13]; India [14]; Singapore and Indonesia [15]; Malaysia [16]. In higher education in the Asian region, there are cases of sexual violence, including in Indonesia. Based on data from Hope Helps as a provider of sexual violence handling services on Indonesian campuses, there were 47 cases of sexual violence between March 2019 and May 2020 [17]. Many cases of sexual violence are not revealed because victims do not dare to report them, this is in line with Khan *et al.* [6] research results from 1,671 surveys conducted by students, only 2.2% dared to report to higher education.

The Indonesian government issues policies through Minister of Education Regulation Number 30 of 2021 concerning the handling and prevention of sexual violence [18]. Based on this regulation, all forms of sexual violence in higher education must be prevented and handled by the entire academic community as an implementation of the Merdeka Campus program, especially freedom from sexual violence in educational institutions. The problem is that not all higher education implements it; lack of relations between the academic community in handling and preventing sexual violence in higher education; there are challenges in preventing and handling sexual violence; There is no model of anti-violence mitigation policy as an effort to handle and prevent sexual violence. Based on this background, researchers are interested in researching mitigating sexual violence in higher education. This study aimed to determine the relationship between policy stakeholders, lecturers, students, and education staff; know the obstacles and challenges; and know the model of sexual violence mitigation policies in higher education to realize a campus free from violence.

2. METHOD

The method used in this research is qualitative with the type of case study research in higher education in Indonesia. Qualitative methods were selected based on the purpose of the study, which was to analyze the mitigation of sexual violence in higher education environments. The case study research was chosen on the grounds of collecting information on empirical facts about the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education. Restrictive research focused on the issue of sexual violence in three higher education areas which have enforced Minister of Education Regulation Number 30 of 2021. The limitations of research related to sexual violence mitigation in higher education can be seen as a sensitive issue raised by researchers so it becomes a challenge in research, especially in maintaining institutional confidentiality, everything related to institutions will be disguised. All three higher education schools have implemented the handling and prevention of sexual violence. In qualitative research, it is important to understand meaning from the perspective of participants. Therefore, participants are determined appropriately to be able to answer the research question. Researchers used purposive sampling techniques in determining participants consisting of three policy supervisors, six lecturers, 12 students, three education staff, and three sexual violence task force teams in higher education.

Data collection was conducted by observation, documentation study, interviews, and focus group discussion (FGD). Observations were made by researchers to determine the behavior of participants directly at the research location [19]. Researchers collected observational data in the form of descriptions of observations of the implementation of the Ministry of Education and Culture in higher education. Interviews were collected to obtain information on the prevention and treatment of sexual violence in higher education from study participants. Researchers conducted interviews with police supervisors in higher education, lecturers, students, education personnel, and task force teams in higher education. The documentation intended in this study is in the form of law documents, rector's decree, various regulations, guidelines, statistical data, photo documents, and research journal documents related to sexual violence in higher education. After the study, the researchers conducted an FGD. Processing research data on sexual violence mitigation in higher education using NVivo 12 Plus, VOSviewer, and Publish or Perish applications. The NVivo 12 Plus device is used to help organize and analyze data to identify appropriate themes NVivo 12 Plus can help researchers visualize research results so that research subjectivity can be avoided [20]. Meanwhile, documentation study data derived from relevant research journals were processed using Publish or Perish and VOSviewer. Researchers use data triangulation to perform data validation, researchers examine different data sources and use it to build justification. While data analysis uses the concepts of Miles and Huberman [21] namely reducing data, presenting data, and concluding.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of sexual violence mitigation research environments were processed using NVivo 12 so that Word Frequency data was obtained to determine the suitability of data analysis with the theme of sexual violence mitigation research in higher education. Figure 1 shows word frequency from sexual violence mitigation research in higher education, showing that various analyses of interview data have been by the research theme, this is evidenced by the word "Violence" is the most in the interview results, which is as many as 458 words; then the word "Sexual" as many as 431 words; while the word "Handling" appears as many as 307 words; the word "Prevention" has 284 words; the word "Campus" is 247 words; While the word "student" as many as 192 words. The results showed that the results of data processing were interrelated with the research theme on sexual violence mitigation in higher education.

Researchers collected various studies from previous research using bibliometric studies on the Publish or application Perish and VOSviewer. The purpose of this previous study is as an overview of

Table 1 Cluster theme related to sexual violence in higher education

Color clusters	Indicators related to sexual violence
Clusters 1 (Red)	Sexual violence on campus; Sexual violence on campus; Campus security; Campus culture; Campus community; Authority campus; Awareness; Impact; Implementation; Institution; Help; Garden; Justice; Knowledge; Law; Me Too; Policy; Reason; Procedure; Report; Answer; Security; Prevention of Sexual violence; Survivors of sexual violence; Sexual violence policy; Student; Country; Trauma; Training; University.
Clusters 2 (Green)	Comparison; Depression; Discrimination; Friend; Gender; Abuse; Influence; Interpersonal Violence; intimate partner sexual violence; mental health; physical violence; Relationship; Risk; Gender; Victimization of sexual violence; Sexual minorities; Victimization of sexual violence; Sexuality; Violence.
Clusters 3 (Dark blue)	Affirmative Consent; Attack; Attention; sexual violence on campus; Change; Challenge; Higher Education Campus; Culture; Fact; Focus; Group; Information; Minority; Rape; Sexual harassment; Sexual harassment; Sexual violence; Support; Woman
Clusters 4 (Yellow)	Alcohol use; Association; University; Result; Experience; Factor; Woman; Interest; Man; Perp; Reaction; Sexual acts; Sexual conduct; Sexual coercion; Sexual contact
Clusters 5 (Purple)	Mock; Action; Activism; Sexual violence on campus; Community; Attention; Diversity; Intention; Intervention; Margin; Kind; Rape Culture; Relationship; Responsibility; Role; Situation
Clusters 6 (Light blue)	Approach; Attitude; Higher education campus; Education; Evaluation; Intervention program; Perspective; Power; Exercise; Preventing sexual violence; sexual aggression; Prevention of sexual violence; Strategy
Clusters 7 (Orange)	Effect; Effort; Examination; Frequency; Investigation; Measure; sexual violence; sexual victimization; Stalking; Victim
Clusters 8 (Brown)	Campus crime; Campus violence; Consideration; dating violence; Effectiveness; Prevention programs; Problem; Relationship Violence
Clusters 9 (Pink)	Physical sexual violence; Sexual violence in disability

3.1. Interaction between policy stakeholders, lecturers, students, and education staff

The interaction between policy makers, lecturers, students, and education staff takes concepts from Giddens' structuration theory which believes that the relationship between structure and agent is duality. The main theoretical propositions of structuration Giddens saw structure as rules and resources, which are involved in the production and reproduction of social actions, as well as being a means of reproduction of systems (duality of structures) [30]. Based on Figure 4 shows that Giddens' structuration theory looks at modalities or intermediate means of duality of structure and interaction, to relate agent capacity to structure. Agents whose role is to use intermediary means (interpretive, facilities, norms) about structures (signification, dominance, and legitimacy) and systems of interaction (communication, power, and sanctions). The above three dimensions of structure according to Giddens [31] are resources (which are focused on significance and legitimacy) which are the nature of social systems that are structured, generated, and reproduced by qualified knowledgeable agents during interaction. These three dimensions can be linked to revealing the phenomenon of sexual violence in higher education. Although Giddens speaks on a conceptual level rather than empirical research, his theory can be an analytical knife on the process of duality between structure and agent in an attempt to prevent and treat sexual violence.

The structure in question is a policy guide in higher education that has an important role in supporting the implementation of the Minister of Education in the handling and prevention of sexual violence. Efforts made by higher education in strengthening governance related to legitimacy ratified the rector's regulation on the handling and prevention of sexual violence, including ratifying various rules, guidelines, operational standards, and various policies regarding the handling and prevention of sexual violence on campus. The significance of policymakers is very related to regulations for the handling and prevention of sexual violence so that they can make policy rules, provide support for facilities and infrastructure, and support operational activities. The dominance of policy-making structures in higher education is very important so that it can influence the academic community in providing guarantees of campus comfort and safety that is free from sexual violence.

Figure 4. The concept of duality Giddens structuration [32]

The importance of cooperation between structures in higher education includes rectors, vice-rectors, deans, heads of study programs, and structural officials in higher education with the academic community in the handling and prevention of sexual violence. If there is no synergy between policymakers and the academic community, it can cause problems such as lack of coordination at the Top Down, lack of communication, hampering the performance of the task force sexual violence in higher education, as well as the lack of infrastructure and budget support provided in efforts to prevent and address sexual violence. As revealed by the sexual violence task force team in higher education on campus C as:

"The task force on sexual violence in higher education on campus C hopes that there will be joint discussions with campus policy supervisors to meet the needs of facilities and infrastructure, as well as the provision of special budgets for the handling and prevention of sexual violence on campus, many obstacles are faced without interference from campus." (Interview with sexual violence task force in higher education campus C, 2023)

The dominance of policy supervisors is very important, this has been regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Education Number 30 of 2021 Article 37, which that the leadership facilitates the implementation of the duties and authorities of the task force including infrastructure support, operational support, and security and legal protection [18]. Like previous research, the structure of the campus supports efforts to prevent sexual violence in higher education [29].

Agents who play a role in using modalities are lecturers, students, education staff, and the entire campus community. Interpretive socialization regarding the handling and prevention of sexual violence needs to be carried out for all academicians because not all academicians know about the forms of sexual violence that often occur in everyday life, even if there are cases of community members who do not know where to report or do not want to report. Understanding of sexual violence for students is carried out through various academic and non-academic activities, such as campus introduction activities for new students; socialization through social media; seminar activities; and study of the learning module on sexual violence prevention and handling that can be accessed in E-Learning; through direct learning in the classroom that is integrated with learning about the handling and prevention of sexual violence; Introductory lectures for students to practice studying outside the campus to be free from sexual violence during internships; Through informal student activities, student associations and student communities on campus. As stated by the student community:

"Students create a community "Mobilize Together Against Sexual Violence" as an effort by students as agents of change who care about voicing Freedom from sexual violence in efforts to prevent sexual violence, both through social media and direct activities to other students." (Interview with campus C students, 2023)

Involvement of lecturers in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence to provide understanding to students both through classroom learning and through the involvement of socialization activities; joint research on the theme of violence; and conducting community service activities to spread understanding to the community about the handling and prevention of sexual violence. Education personnel have a role in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence on campus. The academic community must be facilitated to be able to carry out efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence, including facilities in socialization activities, seminars, training on the handling and prevention of sexual violence; the existence of a special room for the sexual violence task force in higher education; counseling room; reporting facilities both online and offline; including the provision of closed circuit television (CCTv), especially in places prone to violence; sufficient illumination at night; providing medical facilities, legal aid, psychologists; and so on. The academic community is also required to comply with norms in the form of both written and unwritten rules in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence in higher education, including timing of the academic community on campus; final project guidance rules; establishment of a code of ethics; Including guidelines for preventing and handling sexual violence on campus.

A good interaction system between agents and structures produces synergies. Well-established communication between policymakers and the academic community, including with the sexual violence task force in higher education so that efforts to handle and prevent sexual violence can run smoothly. As stated by the speaker:

"The sexual violence task force in higher education always maintains good communication with the campus so that all needs are met, including various sexual violence prevention and handling activities with full support. Communication is also established with the academic community through direct contact, "Pick Up the Ball" so that the academic community is well educated about the handling and prevention of sexual violence." (Interview with campus task force A, 2023)

Policymakers who have the power to make rules on campus; and organize the academic community to prevent and handle sexual violence on campus, including arranging for academicians who are proven to have committed sexual violence to be sanctioned, policy supervisors will be given recommendations for handling sexual violence cases on campus including recommendations for sanctions to be imposed on perpetrators. Sanctions must be given fairly by applicable rules, sanctions are imposed strictly regardless of position; Deter the perpetrator of his actions, and not repeat his mistakes. It can be concluded that Giddens' structuration theory emphasizes the synergistic relationship between policy-making structures and the entire academic community in the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education.

Research on sexual violence mitigation in higher education uses the analysis knife of Giddens structuration theory and is combined with a gender perspective. Previous research related gender structuring to see women having obstacles in power structures, gender structuring theory was used to see women's constraints in gender power structures due to patriarchal dominance [33]. Women are mostly sexual victims, as data shows that women aged 18-24 years are 3x at risk, even 1 in 5 women experience sexual violence [11], [34], [35]. Surveys show that 1 in 3 students have experienced sexual violence, and even 1 in 20 students have experienced sexual violence in higher education since the first college [36]. This is in line with research conducted by researchers at Campuses A, B, and C, all victims are mostly women. Importance for policymakers In establishing policies that prioritize gender mainstreaming in higher education [37], [38]; provide a safe and comfortable space for educated women; facilitate reporting for victims of violence by safeguarding the identity of victims; provide legal guarantees and psychological assistance for women who experience sexual violence on campus; and ensure that victims of violence continue their studies, and continue their careers in higher education; building a campus culture that is safe for women; provide space for women to innovate, achieve; Eliminate all forms of violence and discrimination. The academic community together respects and respects each other to create an environment that is safe from violence, not tolerating all forms of violence; and create an educational environment free from sexual violence.

Research on sexual violence mitigation in higher education involves structures that play a role in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence in higher education, such as the existence of policy-making structures regulating the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education based on justice and gender equality. In addition, the importance of agent involvement in efforts to prevent sexual violence in higher education such as students, lecturers, and education staff. Without the involvement of these agents, various policies at the structural level will not be able to work and vice versa if without the support of policymakers' efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence on campus cannot be implemented properly. Therefore, there is a need for collaboration between structures and agents in the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education.

3.2. Obstacles and challenges

Since enacting the Regulation of the Minister of Education Number 30 of 2021 concerning the handling and prevention of sexual violence in universities in Indonesia, of course, not all universities have implemented it well. There are obstacles faced in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence in higher education, including the lack of: i). support from policymakers; ii). operational support; iii). Support for facilities and facilities; iv). support from the campus community in increasing understanding and awareness; v). Human resources involved in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence; vi). cooperation with referral parties such as hospitals, psychologists, psychiatrists, legal institutions, and related referral agencies; vii). The division of time and work for the sexual violence task force on campus.

The challenges that must be faced in preventing and handling sexual violence in higher education are when enforcing anti-sexual violence rules in universities but faced with legal problems, and the importance of legal protection for the task force so that it can work optimally. The problem of sexual violence cases in higher education can come from internal and external cases, so the challenge is if there is a case of violence where the perpetrator or victim comes from another university, it requires cooperation from various parties across universities. The challenge for universities is to uncover instances of sexual violence and resolve them with administrative sanctions according to existing rules so that new cases are not handled after going viral on social media.

Another challenge faced is the many problems of sexual violence involving perpetrators of sexual violence that occur in cyberspace. Sexual violence in cyberspace is an important issue, various studies on sexual violence in the digital space [31], [39], [32], Digital track records are difficult to monitor so that the spread of pornography will be fast and cannot be erased, so it requires various experts in the field of information technology or digital forensics experts in handling cases of sexual violence in the digital world. Perpetrators of sexual violence in the digital world will be difficult to find. This is a challenge in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence both in real and cyberspace.

The various obstacles and challenges faced by universities in preventing and handling sexual violence must certainly involve all parties, including lecturers, students, education staff, all campus residents,

local governments, and the central government. Various policies that lead to the prevention and handling of sexual violence in higher education uphold partiality towards victims, especially siding with women, most of whom are victims of sexual violence.

3.3. Model of anti-violence mitigation policy in higher education

The purpose of overcoming sexual violence in higher education can be seen in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence. In the prevention aspect, a pattern of structural agent linkage can be developed: i) The involvement of policy-making structures in strengthening governance, including making rules regarding the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education; supporting the existence of supporting infrastructure; and budget and activity support. ii) The involvement of lecturers in higher education Tri dharma activities includes education; research; and community service in implementing the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education. iii) Student involvement in academic activities; non-academic; and strengthening student communities against sexual violence in higher education. iv) Involvement of education personnel in the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education. v) A task force team that has competent human resources in the field of prevention and handling of violence cases, especially in the fields of law, social, and psychology; has the task of socializing and handling cases of sexual violence in higher education; carry out various activities that support the implementation of Minister of Education Regulation Number 30 of 2021; The task force has very important goals and benefits so support is needed for the realization of higher education that is safe from sexual violence. The synergy of the academic community together against sexual violence in higher education, if agents play roles such as students, lecturers, and education staff as well as the sexual violence task force team in higher education, will not work without support from structures such as policymakers who have the power to provide funding, infrastructure, and strengthen governance in higher education. However, on the contrary, if policymakers support the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education without the support of the academic community, it becomes less effective.

Prevention and treatment can be done by higher education in various ways. Prevention of sexual violence in higher education environments by doing: i) higher education has procedures regarding socialization and education activities in prevention efforts; ii) have various forms of socialization activities; iii) organizing various trainings both for the task force and for the academic community on the handling and prevention of sexual violence; iv) it should be considered in prevention efforts by limiting the time of activities on campus not until late at night; v) in addition, arrangements regarding places prone to sexual violence such as campus hallways are illuminated; the presence of CCTV; vi) arrangement of tutoring places for students on campus; Arrangement of places of activity for the academic community both in academic and non-academic activities. Handling carried out by higher education by carrying out activities: i) assistance, especially to the whistleblower to provide a sense of security to report and ensure that the whistleblower is kept confidential, ii) protection both socially and legally, iii) providing academic sanctions for the academic community who are proven to have committed sexual violence, iv) recovery from trauma to victims, v) Provide a reporting system that is easily accessible to all academics, both in the form of online and offline reporting come directly to the place of the task force for the handling and prevention of sexual violence on campus, vi) have procedures for handling both victims and perpetrators of sexual violence.

The recommendations of this study provide a model for mitigating sexual violence in higher education, namely: i) mitigation of sexual violence based on justice and gender equality; ii) participatory based sexual violence mitigation of the academic community, both policy supervisors, lecturers, students, education staff, and the community in the higher education environment; iii) combating sexual violence based on planning and implementing prevention and handling programs; iv) mitigation that can face various obstacles and challenges in the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education; v) countermeasures of sexual violence that can be monitored and evaluated periodically in higher education and education ministries; and vi) mitigation of sexual violence from the bottom up so that it can receive input from the academic community both to stakeholders in higher education and the ministry of education. It can be concluded that this study can recommend a participatory sexual violence mitigation policy model for the academic community based on gender equality and justice. Policies must be able to give birth to sexual violence mitigation programs in higher education that are tailored to the needs of the academic community so that the policy is considered outdated and ineffective, and there is a view that sexual violence is caused by the existence of broader patriarchal symptoms in society and is difficult to eliminate [40]. Various parties work together to create higher education that is free from violence.

Previously, there has been research related to sexual violence prevention in higher education [41] [42]; the importance of building a campus climate [43]; data-based sexual violence handling [13], [44]; disclosure policy regarding sexual violence violations [45]; prevention can be done by forming communities [46]; sex education [47]; become an observer of sexual violence prevention [34], [48]; [49]; Services for

victims of violence [47]. However, no one has discussed the mitigation of sexual violence in universities. There needs to be a strategy in implementing anti-sexual violence in universities, as explained in previous research, violence mitigation must be flexible in paying attention to the influence of social, medical, psychological [50], because the problem of sexual violence is a complex problem.

The solution offered in this study requires a transformation of higher education structure policies that specifically regulate sexual violence prevention based on gender equality and justice, so there needs to be collaboration of academic community agents in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence in higher education. Certain higher education can be a role model for the implementation of Minister of Education Regulation Number 30 of 2021 concerning the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education in Indonesia. Sexual violence in higher education is an important problem that needs to be found a solution so that presenting an independent campus from sexual violence is a priority for the implementation of higher education in Indonesia so that it can encourage higher education to give birth to a generation of nations that have superior and ethical Human Resources. This can be realized by creating a safe, comfortable higher education atmosphere, and can also create a generation that is intellectually and spiritually intelligent, emotionally, socially, and characterful by the values of the Indonesian nation.

4. CONCLUSION

The results showed that the phenomenon of sexual violence in higher education is like an iceberg phenomenon that does not appear on the surface even though many cases occur. Various efforts are made in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence both carried out by higher education to the ministry of higher education in Indonesia. There are obstacles and challenges in the implementation of Minister of Education Regulation Number 30 of 2021 concerning the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education in Indonesia. Research on sexual violence mitigation in higher education involves structures that play a role in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence in higher education, such as the existence of policy-making structures regulating the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education based on justice and gender equality. In addition, the importance of agent involvement in efforts to prevent sexual violence in higher education such as students, lecturers, and education staff. Without the involvement of these agents, various policies at the structural level will not be able to work and vice versa if without the support of policymakers' efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence on campus cannot be implemented properly.

The solution offered in this study requires a transformation of higher education structure policies that specifically regulate sexual violence prevention based on gender equality and justice, so there needs to be collaboration of academic community agents in efforts to prevent and handle sexual violence in higher education. Policies on the prevention and handling of sexual violence in universities need to be further analyzed how the strategy and implementation are, so that dissatisfaction with university policies on sexual violence do not arise.

Higher education can be a role model for the implementation of Minister of Education Regulation Number 30 of 2021 concerning the handling and prevention of sexual violence in higher education in Indonesia. This study provides recommendations for participatory sexual violence mitigation policy models from the entire academic community based on gender equality and justice that can be applied in Indonesia. All must run synergistically between the government, campus leaders, and the academic community together hand in hand in preventing and handling sexual violence in higher education so that it can present a sense of security and comfort in realizing a campus free from sexual violence.

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